

DETECTING CYBERBULLYING ACROSS NIGERIAN LANGUAGES: A MULTILINGUAL SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

As the digital world evolves, the issue of cyberbullying continues to escalate, affecting individuals across diverse cultural and linguistic contexts. While significant progress has been made in developing efficient cyberbullying detection systems primarily in English, these solutions have reached a saturation point, limiting their applicability and effectiveness in non-English speaking environments. This paper presents a comprehensive multilingual cyberbullying detection system designed to identify and address instances of online harassments in two languages used in Nigeria –Pidgin and Igbo. A prototype is developed that operates across data sets created for these two languages. Using this prototype, experiments are carried out with Multinomial Naive Bayes (MNB), Logistics Regression (LR), and Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) algorithms to detect cyberbullying in these two languages. The results of our experiments show an accuracy up-to 97% and F1-score up-to 96% on datasets for both the languages.

KEYWORDS: Cyberbullying, Machine Learning, Multilingual, Nigerian languages, Detection

1. INTRODUCTION

According to Alsafari et al. (2020), Social media has become one of the most powerful platforms for sourcing information, expressing opinions and feelings as well as posting of multimedia contents. People communicate freely and anonymously with one another through these platforms irrespective of geographical locations. However, the sharing of hateful content and online harassment is becoming a menace in these online communities (Williams et.al. 2019). Cyberbullying is a form of bullying that occurs through digital platforms such as social media, websites, text messages, and online gaming. It involves the use of technology to harass, threaten, embarrass or intimidate individuals, often targeting vulnerable populations, including children and teenagers. The effects of cyberbullying are often devastating on such population and they result in victims having lower self-esteem. Bullying can also cause many negative effects such as impacts on the mental and physical health, depression and anxiety, and can lead to suicidal

tendencies. Hence, cyberbullying is an epidemic that needs to be controlled quickly and effectively.

Facebook, Twitter and other social media platforms have implemented various countermeasures to combat cyberbullying and create safer online environments. These strategies include reporting systems whereby users are allowed to report abuse or harassing content. Users can flag posts, comments or messages that they feel are harmful, which are often reviewed by platform moderator. Social media platforms employ both automated algorithms and human moderators to monitor content for offensive language, hate speech or harassment. These systems can identify and remove harmful content before it spreads widely. Also, social media companies develop and publish clear community guidelines that outline acceptable behaviors. The guidelines serve as a framework for both users and moderators when addressing inappropriate interactions. Some platforms offer tools that help users manage their interactions more effectively. For example, features may include the ability to block or mute users, restrict who can comment on a user's posts or filter certain words in comments.

According to Pauer & Raje (2019), most of the prevalent approaches to automatically detect cyberbullying focus on English text and associated forums. However, a large number of mobile device users are in African countries such as Nigeria, Ghana, Cameroon and Gambia where social media has become very popular in the 21st century (Mohd Noorhadi & Zurinah Tahir 2017; Balasundran et al., 2021). Statistics show Igbo is a major language, with estimates ranging from over 46 million speakers, making it the third or fourth largest language group after Hausa and Yoruba in Nigeria. Pidgin on its part boasts massive numbers with recent 2025 estimates placing it at 121 million speakers making it a leading language in Africa and globally, used widely across Nigeria and west Africa as crucial lingua franca, uniting diverse groups despite lacking official status (Yakpo, 2025).

This paper describes a Multilingual Cyberbullying Detection System for detection of cyberbullying behavior in two Nigerian languages – Pidgin and Igbo, and to examine various machine learning techniques and their effects on the accuracy of detection of cyberbullying messages by empirical evaluations. Hence, the proposed system has a potential of creating a significant impact in making online forums safer for the users of these two languages in Nigeria.

2. BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Some researches in offensive language and hate speech detection for African languages include the work of Mossie and Wang (2018). The authors created a corpus of comments in Amharic language collected from Facebook. The corpus consists of 4882 which were classified as hate or no-hate. A similar dataset for Amharic language hate speech detection was created by Tesfaye and Kakeba (2020).

In the work of Haider et al. (2016), a survey on multilingual cyberbullying detection was carried out and the findings showed that most of the work in this domain is done in English. In another attempt in 2017, they developed a cyberbullying detection system for local dialect such as Arabic language. In their effort, they used ML learning approach to detect cyberbullying. Their dataset contained 32,000 tweets; out of which 1800 tweets were bullying ones. They used Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Naïve Bayes algorithms to detect cyberbullying and achieved F1 scores of 92% and 90% respectively.

Ting et al., (2017) carried out a research in which they gathered a dataset from 4 popular social sites in Taiwan. Social Network Mining technique to detect cyberbullying was used to and identified three features from the data: Keywords, Social Network Analysis, and Sentiment. They indicated that sentiment is the most important feature to detect cyberbullying as it helps to understand the sentiment/intent of user when he posts message on social media. They used precision and recall as performance measurements. The evaluation results show the precision to be around 79% and the recall around 71%.

Silva et al. (2016) developed a mobile app called 'BullyBlocker'. The main aim of their work was to develop a mobile app on the top of a machine learning model. This app not only helps in cyberbullying detection but also send bullying detection alerts to parents. This app crawls the Facebook feed and messages using the Facebooks API and holds the record of bullying behavior for last 60 days.

Zel et al. (2017) prepared a dataset from Instagram and Twitter messages written in Turkish and then applied machine learning techniques SVM, decision tree, Naïve Bayes Multinomial, and k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) classifiers to detect cyberbullying. They applied information gain and chi-square feature selection methods to improve the accuracy of classifiers. They observed that

when both words and emoticons in the text messages are considered as features, cyberbully detection improves. Among the classifiers, Naïve Bayes Multinomial was the most successful one in terms both classification accuracy and running time and they achieved 84% accuracy using it.

3. METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the methodology employed to classify bullying words on the Twitter platform using various Machine Learning (ML) models. The approach includes data collection, preprocessing, model selection, training and evaluation.

4. ANALYSIS OF THE PROPOSED DETECTION SYSTEM

This section describes the steps taken to implement the detection system. The system uses the principles of ML, and thus, as a first step, we had to create a dataset for training and testing the ML models. The ML model was created using python's ML framework i.e., scikit-learn. Due to context sensitivity of these local Nigerian dialects, and to ensure correct labeling of messages, we manually labeled the messages in both the pidgin and Igbo datasets. Attribute called “bullying” was used (i.e., output label) – if the value of this attribute is “yes”, it indicates that the message is bullying in nature and a value of “no” indicates the non-bullying behavior. **Dataset**

- **Data Gathering and Labeling:** for this study, we utilized a dataset comprising tweets collected from the Twitter platform. The dataset was curated using the Twitter API focusing on tweets containing terms commonly associated with bullying. In Nigeria, Twitter has become one of the most used social media platforms where people of different culture, religion and political affiliations interacts (Kadijat et.al. 2020). For the Pidgin -related experiments we used 621 tweets. For Igbo language-related experiments we collected 500 tweets.
- **Data Pre-processing:** Before model training, several preprocessing steps were undertaken to enhance the quality of the data.
 - **Text cleaning:** First was the text cleaning step which involves removing special characters, URLs and emojis to simplify the text for analysis. The dataset obtained

contained lot of unnecessary characters (such as #, @ etc.), stop-words, URLs, punctuations and user ids. So, the first task after data gathering is to remove such unwanted words/characters. For instance “@uchebenzene008498 “ùtùrù gbagbuo gi”. This tweet contains entities that are unnecessary and not required for training the ML model.

- **Tokenization:** Tweets were tokenized into individual words (tokens) for further analysis.
- **Stop words removal:** Commonly used words (stop words) that carry little emetic meaning were removed from the dataset to focus on more informative terms.
- **Stemming/Lemmatization:** Words were reduced to their base root form to consolidate variations of the same word.
- **Synthetic Data Generation:** After manual tagging of the data set, we realized that dataset of both the language contained approximately 11% of bullying messages. Hence, in order to avoid any data imbalance issue, we decided to generate additional instances of bullying messages from the existing instances. The cyberbullying words were doubled so that resulting dataset will have at least 20% bullying messages.

- **Feature Extraction**

To facilitate the classification process, we employed feature extraction method by converting the preprocessed string data into the Bag of Words (BoW) format. The BoW format disregards grammar and the order of the words but retains the frequency of the words. The BoW technique is the most common and effective approach used in the text classification problem. We have used the BoW format for all of our experiments. We have also performed 10-fold cross validation for all our experiments. This means that each data point appears only once in the test dataset and 9 times in the training dataset. The purpose of 10-fold validation is, to generalize the model by computing the average error across the folds, no matter how the data is divided.

- **Model Selection**

We compared the performance of several machine learning models to determine the most effective classifier for our task. These models selected were because they perform well on topic modeling and text classification. The models chosen for the evaluation are:

- Multinomial Naive Bayes (MNB)
- Logistic Regression (LR)
- Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)

- **Model Training**

Each selected model was trained using a train-test split strategy. The dataset was partitioned into a training set (80%) and a test set (20%). Cross-validation techniques were also applied to ensure robustness and avoid over fitting during training.

- **Model Evaluation**

To evaluate the performance of each model, we employed several metrics with a primary focus on the F1 score which balances precision and recall, providing a comprehensive assessment of the models' effectiveness in classifying bullying-related content. The metrics are shown as follows:

- Accuracy: this metric measure the number of tweets correctly classified. It is calculated as: $Accuracy = (TP + TN) / T$
- Precision = $TP / (TP + FP)$
- Recall: This metric measure how many bullying tweets, out of all available ones, are actually detected by the algorithm. It is calculated as: $Recall = TP / (TP + FN)$
- F1-Score: This metric computed using the harmonic mean of precision and recall. F1-Score is calculated by the following formula: $F = 2 * (Precision * Recall) / (Precision + Recall)$

Where

TP: number of true positive

TN: number of true negative

FP: number of false positive

FN: number of false negative

T: total number of tweets

5. RESULTS

The experiments were conducted using the Multinomial Naive Bayes (MNB), Logistics Regression (LR), and Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) algorithms. There were two phases of experiments namely; experiments with synthesized dataset and experiments without synthesized dataset. From the results obtained, the indication is that that Logistics Regression (LR) outperforms Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) and Multinomial Naive Bayes (MNB) in all the languages.

MNB has the assumption that every feature is independent but that is not possible in real situations – thus, it does not outperform LR in our experiments as well. LR performs well for the binary classification problem and continues to work better as data size grows. LR updates a set of parameters in an iterative manner and tries to minimize the error function whereas, SGD uses one sample and uses the close approximation to update the parameters. Hence, SGD performs faster but error is not as minimized as in LR. So, it is not surprising that LR outperforms the other two approaches in our experiments as well. Results in Tables I & II also show that our model performs as expected, even when we add more data to create the synthesized dataset. Accuracy is not good measure to compare performance of the model especially when dataset is imbalanced; hence, we use F1-score as the performance measure. Results with the synthesized dataset (Tables I & II,) show that the addition of more data to our dataset improves the F1 score. This indicates that our model is generalized and performs better on both the classes (i.e., bullying and non-bullying) than when it is created with the imbalanced (i.e., actual) dataset.

TABLE I RESULT FOR PIDGIN DATASET

S/n	Algorithm	Synthesize data	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
1.	MNB	No	0.7893	0.9434	0.8157	0.8748
		Yes	0.9656	0.9685	0.9654	0.9657
2.	SGD	No	0.8155	0.9433	0.8159	0.8746
		Yes	0.9485	0.9537	0.9482	0.9485
3.	LR	No	0.8235	0.9324	0.8235	0.8954
		Yes	0.9657	0.9646	0.9666	0.9689

TABLE II RESULT FOR IGBO DATASET

S/n	Algorithm	Synthesize data	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
1.	MNB	No	0.8780	0.8865	0.8780	0.8792
		Yes	0.8845	0.8974	0.8895	0.8845
2.	SGD	No	0.9232	0.9257	0.9045	0.9177
		Yes	0.9352	0.9365	0.9135	0.9263
3.	LR	No	0.9311	0.9311	0.9312	0.9307
		Yes	0.9424	0.9421	0.9438	0.9412

6. CONCLUSION

This paper has provided a cyberbullying detection approach across languages using cyberbullying messages from tweets for two Nigerian local dialects. Results of our experiments show that Logistics Regression outperforms all other algorithms on the datasets. Also, generating synthesized data could help us improve performance of our system. Results of our study show that our systems perform well across two languages and it can be used to detect cyberbullying for other Nigerian languages.

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